

ALGEBRAIK ANIQLIGI YUQORI BO`LGAN KVADRATUR FORMULALAR. GAUSS KVADRATUR FORMULALARI.

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Yangi O`zbekistonimizda yuz berayotgan siyosiy, iqtisodiy, ilmiy – texnikaviy va madaniy o`zgarishlar Oliy ta`lim tizimida ham o`z aksini topmoqda. O`zbekistonda uzluksiz ta`lim – tarbiya tizimini yaratish, shu asosida ta`lim sifatini jahon andozalari darajasiga yetkazish ta`lim sistemasining eng dolzarb vazifasiga aylandi.

Hisoblash matematikasi sohasida nazariy izlanishlar asosan, tipik matematik masalalarni yechishning sonli metodlar atrofida guruhlanadi. Bu sohaning klassik masalalaridan biri bu integrallarni taqribiy hisoblash formulalarini qurishdan iborat.

Bir karrali integrallarni son qiymatlari geometrik nuqtai nazardan qisqacha kvadratura deb ataladi.

Bunday masalalar bilan ko`pincha buyuk olimlar shug`ullanganlar. Masalan: Gauss, Chebishev, Eyler, Nyuton va boshqalar.

Kvadratur formular deganda quyidagi taqribiy tenglikni tushunamiz:

$$\int_B f(x)dx \approx \sum_{\lambda=1}^N C_{\lambda} f(x^{(\lambda)}), \quad (1)$$

bu yerda C_{λ} – kvadratur formulaning koeffisientlari, $x^{(\lambda)}$ – tugun nuqtalari, N – tugun nuqtalar soni[2].

Faraz qilaylik $f(x)$ uzluksiz funksiyani $[a, b]$ kesmada aniq integralni taqribiy hisoblovchi formulani qurish talab qilinsin.

Integralning eng sodda taqribiy ifodasi asosan $[a, b]$ kesma balandligi $f(x)$ ning $\frac{a+b}{2}$ nuqtadagi $f(\frac{a+b}{2})$ qiymatiga teng bo`lgan to`g`ri turtburchak yuzasining kattaligidan iborat.

Quyidagi kvadratur formulani hosil qilamiz.

$$\int_a^b f(x)dx \approx (b-a)f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right), \quad (2)$$

Katta nazariy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan kvadratur formulalar bilan bog'liq hisoblash algoritmlarini optimizizastiyalash masalalari bilan ko'pgina olimlar shug'ullanib kelgan[3-4]. Bulardan S.L.Sobolev, A.N.Kolmogorov, S.M.Nikolskiy va boshqalar.

Kvadratur formulani $p(x)$ - vazn funksiyasi bilan qaraydigan bo'lsak

$$\int_a^b p(x)f(x)dx \approx \sum_{\lambda=1}^N C_{\lambda}f(x^{(\lambda)}), \quad (3)$$

ko'rinishda bo'ladi.

Bu holda xatolik funksionali quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi.

$$\ell(x) = p(x)\varepsilon_{[a,b]}(x) - \sum_{\lambda=1}^N C_{\lambda}\delta(x - x^{(\lambda)}), \quad (4)$$

Integrallarni taqribiy hisoblash uchun formula qurish hisoblash matematikasi va sonlar nazariyasining bir sinf masalasini tashkil qiladi. Bunday masalalarni yechish bilan juda ko'p taniqli matematiklar shug'ullanishgan, shuning uchun ham juda ko'p formulalar ularning nomlari bilan ataladi, masalan Nyuton, Eyler, Gauss, Chebishev, Markov formulalarini misol keltirish mumkin. Integrallarni taqribiy hisoblashda integral ostidagi funksiya bir o'zgaruvchili bo'lsa unda kvadratur formula deyiladi, bunday masalalar bilan birinchi bo'lib Sard, Nikolskiylar shug'ullangan, agar integral ostidagi funksiya ikki va undan ortiq o'zgaruvchili bo'lsa unda kubatur formula deyiladi, bunday masalalar bilan birinchi bo'lib Sobolev shug'ullangan.**ALGEBRAIK ANIQLIGI YUQORI BO'LGAN KVADRATUR FORMULALAR. GAUSS KVADRATUR FORMULALARI.**

$$\int_a^b f(x)dx \text{ ni yaqinlashtirish uchun Nyuton - Kotes formulalari, agar } f(x)$$

ko'phad kabi silliq funksiya bo'lsa, yaxshi ishlaydi. Bu Gauss kvadraturasi uchun ham amal qiladi. Shu bilan birga, Gauss formulalari

$$\int_a^b \omega(x)f(x)dx \quad (1)$$

ko'rinishdagi integrallarni hisoblashda ham yaxshi bo'ladi, bunda vazn funksiyasi deb ataladigan $\omega(x)$ integral bo'lishi sharti bilan singulyativlarni o'z

ichiga olishi mumkin. Bunday integralga misol $\int_0^1 (1+x^2) \ln x dx$. Ba`zan

$\int_0^{\infty} e^{-x} \sin x dx$ dagi kabi cheksiz chegaralarni ham joylashtirish mumkin.

Gauss integratsiya formulalari Nyuton – Kotes qoidalari bilan bir xil shaklga ega

$$I = \sum_{i=0}^n A_i f(x_i) \quad (2)$$

bu yerda, avvalgidek, I (1) tenglamadagi integralga yaqinlikni ifodalaydi. Farqi A_i va tugun absissalar x_i vaznlarini aniqlash usulidadir. Nyuton – Kotes integrallashida tugunlar (a, b) larda teng ravishda joylashtirilgan (ya`ni, ularning joylashuvi oldindan belgilangan). Gauss kvadraturasida tugunlar va vaznlar shunday tanlanadiki, (2) tenglama, agar $f(x)$ ko`phad $2n+1$ yoki undan kichik darajali ko`phad bo`lsa, aniq integralni beradi; ya`ni,

$$\int_a^b \omega(x) P_m(x) dx = \sum_{i=0}^n A_i P_m(x_i), \quad m \leq 2n+1 \quad (3)$$

Vaznlar va absissalarni aniqlashning usullaridan biri $P_0(x)=1, P_1(x)=x, P_2(x)=x^2, \dots, P_{2n+1}(x)=x^{2n+1}$ ni almashtirishdir. (3) tenglamada va A_i va x_i noma`lumlar uchun

$$\int_a^b \omega(x) x^j dx = \sum_{i=0}^n A_i x_i^j, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, 2n+1 \quad (4)$$

tenglamani $\int_a^b f(x) dx$ integralni $2n+2$ bo`lgan hol uchun hisoblaymiz.

Misol tariqasida $\omega(x) = e^{-x}, a = 0, b = \infty$ va $n = 1$ bo`lsin. $x_0, x_1, A_0,$ va A_1 ni aniqlovchi to`rtta tenglama quyidagicha:

$$\int_0^{\infty} e^{-x} dx = A_0 + A_1$$

$$\int_0^1 e^{-x} x dx = A_0 x_0 + A_1 x_1$$

$$\int_0^1 e^{-x} x^2 dx = A_0 x_0^2 + A_1 x_1^2$$

$$\int_0^1 e^{-x} x^3 dx = A_0 x_0^3 + A_1 x_1^3$$

(5)

Integrallarni baholagandan so`ng biz quyidagi natijalarni olamiz:

$$A_0 + A_1 = 1$$

$$A_0 x_0 + A_1 x_1 = 1$$

$$A_0 x_0^2 + A_1 x_1^2 = 2$$

$$A_0 x_0^3 + A_1 x_1^3 = 6$$

(6)

Yechim quyidagi ko`rinishda bo`ladi.

$$x_0 = 2 - \sqrt{2} \quad A_0 = \frac{\sqrt{2} + 1}{2\sqrt{2}}$$

$$x_1 = 2 + \sqrt{2} \quad A_1 = \frac{\sqrt{2} - 1}{2\sqrt{2}}$$

Shunday qilib, integrallash formulasi quyidagicha bo`ladi

$$\int_0^{\infty} e^{-x} f(x) dx \approx \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} [(\sqrt{2} + 1)f(2 - \sqrt{2}) + (\sqrt{2} - 1)f(2 + \sqrt{2})] \quad (7)$$

Tenglamalarning chiziqli bo`lmaganligi sababli, bu yondashuv katta n uchun yaxshi ishlamaydi. x_i va A_i ni topishning amaliy usullari ortogonal ko`phadlar va ularning Gauss kvadraturasi bilan bog`liqligi haqida ma`lum bilimlarni talab qiladi. Biroq, bir nechta "klassik" Gauss integratsiya formulalari mavjud bo`lib, ular uchun absissalar va vaznlar katta aniqlik bilan hisoblab chiqilgan va keyin jadvalga kiritilgan. Bu formulalardan ularning ortidagi nazariyani bilmadan

foydalanish mumkin, chunki Gauss integratsiyasi uchun zarur boʻlgan barcha narsa x_i va A_i qiymatlaridir. Agar siz klassik formulalardan tashqariga chiqish niyatida boʻlmasangiz, keyingi ikkita mavzuni oʻtkazib yuborishingiz mumkin.

1. Misol

Gauss integrallashi bilan $\int_{-1}^1 (1-x^2)^{3/2} f(x) dx$ ni hisoblaymiz. (1.1)

Masalaning yechimi. Integral silliq va birliksiz boʻlgani uchun biz Gauss – Legendre kvadraturasidan foydalanishimiz mumkin. Biroq, aniq integralni Gauss –Chebishev formulasi bilan olish mumkin. Biz

$$\int_{-1}^1 (1-x^2)^{3/2} f(x) dx = \int_{-1}^1 \frac{(1-x^2)^2}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} dx \quad (1.2)$$

ni yozamiz.

$f(x) = (1-x^2)^2$ numeratori toʻrtinchi darajali koʻphad boʻlgani uchun Gauss Chebishev kvadraturasi uchta tugun bilan aniq boʻladi.

Tugunlarning absissalari (1.2) tenglamadan olinadi. $n = 2$ ni almashtirsak,

$$x_i = \cos \frac{\pi(2i+1)}{6}, \quad i = 0, 1, 2$$

ni olamiz. Demak,

$$x_0 = \cos \frac{\pi}{6} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

$$x_1 = \cos \frac{\pi}{2} = 0$$

$$x_2 = \cos \frac{5\pi}{6} = -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

Qiymatlar topiladi va (1.1) tenglama

$$\int_{-1}^1 (1-x^2)^{3/2} f(x) dx \approx \frac{\pi}{3} \sum_{i=0}^2 (1-x_i^2)^2 = \frac{\pi}{3} \left[\left(1 - \frac{3}{4}\right)^2 + (1-0)^2 + \left(1 - \frac{3}{4}\right)^2 \right] = \frac{3\pi}{8}$$

ni hosil qiladi.

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